

Producing plant-based beverages from locally grown legumes and legume-cereal mixtures

Problem

Plant-based milk alternatives are predominantly soy-based; however, soybean is poorly adapted to Spanish growing conditions. In addition, soy faces a significant image challenge within the organic sector, as many consumers associate it with tropical deforestation. This perception persists despite the existence of small-scale organic soy production in Spain that is already used in domestic plant-based beverages. As a result, there is growing demand for alternative, locally grown legume species, whose agronomic performance and suitability for plant-based beverage production remain largely unexplored.

Solution

Chickpea (var. Badil), lentil (var. De la Armuña), and grass pea (var. Merkur) were cultivated under organic conditions in Extremadura, Spain. Crops were grown both as monocultures and in mixtures with cereals (oat; oat and spelt; and oat, spelt, and pea) to assess agronomic performance and suitability for diversified cropping systems. The harvested grain was then processed into experimental plant-based beverages by the industry partner Soria Natural S.A., using an optimised wet processing protocol that included enzymatic hydrolysis and UHT sterilisation.

Benefits

Legume-cereal mixtures substantially outperformed monocultures in grain yield. Among the tested combinations, chickpea-oat produced the most palatable drink, and alkaline extraction with bicarbonate significantly improved protein content across all legume species. These results demonstrate the strong potential of locally grown Spanish legumes, alone or in mixtures, to serve as effective alternatives to soybean in plant-based beverage production.

Practical recommendations

- **Grow legumes in mixtures with oat rather than as monocultures** grain yields were 4–70× higher in mixtures than in monocultures under organic conditions (Figure 1). Grass pea + oat was the most productive combination. Lentil monocultures produced near-zero yields under the conditions tested; mixtures with cereals are essential for viable lentil production.

Applicability box

Theme

Legume-based plant-based beverages; legume-cereal intercropping

Keywords

chickpea, lentil, grass pea, oat, plant-based drink, legume-cereal mixture

Context

Organic farming, semi-arid Mediterranean conditions, Extremadura (Spain)

Application time

Autumn (sowing, Oct–Nov) to summer (harvest, June); processing year-round

Required time

One growing season (~7 months) plus post-harvest processing

Period of impact

Short to medium term (one growing season and product development cycle)

Equipment

Small plot combine harvester; colloidal mill; centrifuge; high-pressure homogenizer; UHT sterilizer

Best in

Organic arable cropping systems connected to plant-based food value chains

- Adjust sowing densities based on number of species planted:** For 2-species mixtures, apply 60% of the standard monoculture sowing density per species (120% combined). Use 40% for 3-species and 30% for 4-species mixtures.
- Plant-based beverage production process:** (1) cook legumes and/or cereals for 40–60 min, then mill finely using a colloidal mill; (2) apply enzymatic hydrolysis and saccharification; (3) filter through 200-micron mesh and centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 3 min; (4) adjust Brix content and add stabilizers (e.g. gellan gum, sunflower oil); (5) homogenize at 300 bar; (6) sterilize by UHT at 130°C for 3 seconds.
- Use alkaline extraction (bicarbonate) to improve protein content:** chickpea drinks reached 1.08 g/100 ml vs. 0.51 g/100 ml with standard extraction, approaching soy benchmark levels (Figure 2).
- Chickpea + oat produced the best-tasting drink with a sweet flavour profile,** based on internal judgement. Grass pea is a high-yielding alternative, but alkaloid content must be verified against food safety regulations before use.

Figure 1. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of legume monocultures and legume-cereal mixtures grown under organic conditions for plant-based beverage production (Extremadura, Spain, 2025). Legume species: chickpea, grass pea and lentil; cereal companions: oat (O), spelt (S) and pea (P).

Figure 2. Protein content (g 100 ml⁻¹) of plant-based beverages produced from legume monocultures and legume + oat mixtures using different extraction methods (standard, protease and bicarbonate treatments) by Soria Natural (2025). The dashed red line indicates the approximate protein content of commercial soy-based beverage (~1.0 g/100 ml).

Figure 3. Separation of solid parts through centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 3 minutes. Photo: María Conde Rioll (Soria Natural) and Chickpea-based beverages. From left to right: Chickpea monoculture, chickpea-oat mixture, chickpea-oat-spelt mixture, chickpea-oat-spelt-pea mixture. Photo: María Conde Rioll (Soria Natural)

About this practice abstract

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